

On composed ML architecture for the modelling of complex water supply systems

José Cação^{1*}, Sara Mota², António Andrade-Campos³, Ana Luísa Reis⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Mechanical Engineering, Centre for Mechanical Technology & Automation (TEMA), Intelligent Systems Associate Laboratory (LASI), University of Aveiro, Portugal

*josemaria@ua.pt

Keywords: Composed Model Architecture, Pump Scheduling Problem, Water Supply Systems

ABSTRACT

Water Supply Systems (WSS) constitute crucial infrastructures that ensure water availability for energy production, industrial activities, and human consumption [1]. Current environmental concerns, such as population growth and climate change, have put WSS under significant pressure, forcing water utilities to operate under strict efficiency and sustainability constraints [2]. Given the critical nature of WSS, water utilities rely on computational tools that integrate hydraulic simulation and optimisation to minimise operational costs and maximise energy efficiency. However, traditional hydraulic simulators, such as EPANET and WaterGEMS, require extensive domain-knowledge on the water networks, detailed network parameters often unavailable in practice, and considerable computational resources, limiting their applicability in real-time support and decision-making [3]. Consequently, Machine Learning (ML) techniques have emerged as efficient alternatives to hydraulic simulators [4, 5]. These approaches can learn complex hydraulic relationships from data, approximating the behaviour of complex systems, while enabling fast evaluations, critical for real-time support and decision-making. Furthermore, their implementation is supported by the growing availability of network sensor data [4].

Motivated by this, the current work proposes the development of a data-driven modelling framework designed to replicate the dynamic behaviour of a WSS, based on a composed differential model architecture. Such approach, illustrated in Figure 1, leverages all the above-mentioned advantages of ML-based hydraulic system modelling, while also introducing the decomposition of the complex hydraulic system into two simpler, physically interpretable models. One focuses on pump hydraulics, predicting pump flow responses based on input control actions, *i.e.*, pump status changes, and it can be further decomposed into smaller models for each individual pump (each individual pump model contributing to the overall loss of the pump hydraulics model). The second leverages those initial predictions and focuses on system dynamics. Combining pump flow information with overall network data, including demands and current tank levels, the model estimates tank level variation rates, resulting in a differential architecture.

The decomposed and differentiable nature of the architecture introduces a series of key advantages: (1) instead of having a single “black-box” model, the structure aligns with the underlying physics of the system, splitting control actions (pump operation) from system dynamics (consequent response of the system), and

Figure 1: Proposed composed model architecture.

facilitating interpretation; (2) it complies and is compatible with physics-informed neural network (PINN) principles: instead of having a model that only minimises the error between real data and predictions, physics-based constraints can be introduced specifically for each model, including energy and mass balances (ensuring realistic operation), or pump-specific characteristic curves for the initial sub-model; (3) it allows for independent and weighted training and optimisation of each sub-model, allowing for individual refinements of each component or for emphasising the overall training importance of each sub-model; (4) and finally, its differential nature means the model is inherently time-agnostic, as it directly outputs the rate of change in each tank's level with time. Consequently, model training does not require data with a fixed sampling interval, and predictions can be evaluated over time steps by numerical integration, allowing flexible temporal resolution.

The architecture's implementation as an integrator and simulator for optimisation is illustrated in Figure 2. For each individual time step of the simulation, the model receives the current system's state as input. This includes pump status, demands, and tank levels. The pump hydraulics model predicts pump flow responses based on the control actions. Then, the second model for systems dynamics leverages that output, in combination with the current network state, to output the tank level variation rates for the upcoming time horizon. Based on the following simulation time-step, the integrator easily calculates the estimated tank levels for the subsequent time-step, and the ML-based hydraulic simulation is conducted for the entire optimisation process.

The differentiable nature of the proposed approach becomes highly beneficial when combined with optimisation. In a recent work, Brás et al. [6] proposed a hybrid optimisation approach, focused on pump scheduling optimisation, that

Figure 2: Deploying the composed model as an integrator, replacing the hydraulic simulator.

outperforms previous methods. However, since it combines a gradient-based algorithm with a hydraulic simulator, its computational cost quickly grows for complex WSS. Since conventional simulators, such as EPANET, do not expose analytical sensitivities with respect to decision variables, the gradient-based method is forced to run $N+1$ (N being the number of decision variables) simulations per optimisation iteration to approximate the Jacobian and gradient matrix, subsequently used to determine the next iteration solution. Conversely, and as demonstrated in [3], a differential model directly outputs these differential responses, enabling the construction of the Jacobian and gradient matrices without running extra simulations, thereby eliminating the need for finite-difference perturbations. Over many iterations, this approach significantly reduces processing times and computational cost of the overall optimisation framework, and making it much more adequate for real-time decision support systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the FEDER and the Regional Operational Program of the Center Region (CENTRO2030) through projects I-ReTiS-LeaksD&Op n° 17304 (CENTRO2030-FEDER-01177300) and n° 16946 (COMPETE2030-FEDER-00823400), funded by PITD under SACCCT by IC&DT, with the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. (FCT) as intermediary beneficiary. Additional support was provided by project I-ReTiS-Leaks (2024.07270.IACDC, <https://doi.org/10.54499/2024.07270.IACDC>) funded under measure “RE-C05-i08.m04 – Support the launch of a program of R&D projects aimed at the development and implementation of advanced cybersecurity systems, artificial intelligence and data science in public administration, as well as a scientific training program” of the Recovery and Resilience Plan – PRR, within the financing contract established between the Estrutura de Missão Recuperar Portugal (EMRP) and the FCT, I.P., as intermediary beneficiary. This work was also supported by national funds from FCT under the project UID 00481/2025 - Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation, <https://doi.org/10.54499/UID/00481/2025>.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Burrow e A. Newman, «Optimal design and operation of River Basin Storage», *Omega*, vol. 95, p. 102061, set. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.omega.2019.04.004.
- [2] W. Rosińska, J. Jurasz, K. Przestrzelska, K. Wartalska, e B. Kaźmierczak, «Climate change’s ripple effect on water supply systems and the water-energy

nexus – A review», *Water Resources and Industry*, vol. 32, p. 100266, dez. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.wri.2024.100266.

[3] S. Mota, T. C. Pereira, A. L. Sousa, M. Brás, A. Reis, e A. Andrade-Campos, «Differential Machine Learning Model for Simulation of Water Supply Systems», *J. Water Resour. Plann. Manage.*, vol. 151, n.º 9, p. 04025044, set. 2025, doi: 10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-6698.

[4] J. Ye, N. C. Do, W. Zeng, e M. Lambert, «Physics-informed neural networks for hydraulic transient analysis in pipeline systems», *Water Research*, vol. 221, p. 118828, ago. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2022.118828.

[5] Z. Y. Wu, M. El-Maghraby, e S. Pathak, «Applications of Deep Learning for Smart Water Networks», *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 119, pp. 479–485, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2015.08.870.

[6] M. Brás, A. Moura, e A. Andrade-Campos, «A novel hybrid optimization approach for cost-efficient pump scheduling in water supply systems», *Omega*, vol. 138, p. 103378, 2026, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2025.103378>.